

Impact of Laboratory Strategy on Interest, Performance and Retention in Biology among Secondary School Students in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated impact of laboratory strategy on interest, academic performance and retention in Biology among secondary school students in Katsina State-Nigeria. The study was guided by three research objectives, corresponding research questions and null hypotheses, respectively. The study employed quasi-experimental research design. The population covered 4,531 male and female senior secondary school class two (SS II) Biology students from 16 public senior secondary schools in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance (ZEQA), Katsina State-Nigeria. The sample size consists of 90 Male and Female students drawn from three schools using cluster and random sampling techniques by balloting technique. Two validated instruments with reliability coefficient of 0.64 and 0.76 using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and Cronbach Alpha method respectively, namely; Biology Performance Test (BPT) and Biology Interest Scale (BIS) were used for data collection. The Mean and Standard-deviation were used to answered research questions while t-test independent were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of Significance. The findings revealed that there is significant differences in interest, performance and retention between students taught Biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method. Based on the findings it was concluded that laboratory strategy served as a better strategy toward having a better interest, performance and retention in Biology. The study recommends among others that Biology teachers should employ the laboratory strategy in teaching Biology at senior secondary school level.

Keywords: Interest, Performance, Retention, Laboratory strategy, Lecture Method

Introduction

The future of every nation including Nigeria lies on the quality of education given to its citizens. Education remains the bedrock of civilization and development of any nation and also one of the most promising paths for individuals to realize better and more productive lives. This is because an individual who acquire knowledge especially scientific and technological literacy, think innovatively and rationally, thus enabling them to conduct themselves within the global acceptable standard. Without good and quality education no any nation can move from where it is to the next stage (Buba & Marcel 2019).

The twenty first century has witnessed the agitation for improvement of students' performance through provision of quality education, in 2015, United Nations has proposed the 2030 Agenda for sustainable development and outlined 17 sustainable development goals, which quality education is among the top agendas for all the United Nations members, being developed or developing countries, (Martin, Arora, 2012; Anna 2017). In line with Republic of Kenya as stated that Education should assist in developing an all-rounded individual personality who is able to develop physically, mentally, socially and morally (KNEC, 2013; Republic of Kenya, 2015). This indicates that for every nation to attain and sustain national development, a well-planned and implemented policies on education, especially science and technological education should be given priority, (Tafi, 2016; Habila & Benjamin, 2020).

The overmentioned points showcased the significance of qualitative education in relation to the national development. In the same manner science education is receiving much emphasis in the world because of its significance and relevance to the life of an individual and society at large. Nigeria as a nation it made several efforts towards the realization of science and appropriate methods for teaching it. Biology is among the science subject taught at secondary schools' level and prerequisite subject for many important fields of learning like medicine, forestry, agriculture, biotechnology and nursing among others that contributes immensely to the technological growth of the nations, (Buba & Marcel 2019).

Biology is a branch of science that deals with study of structure, function, growth, evolution, and distribution of organisms, (Michael, 2012). In simple term Biology, is the study of life or living things, which includes human-beings. Biology has many branches which includes; zoology, botany, ecology, genetics, morphology, anatomy, physiology, histology, microbiology, evolution, cell biology, parasitology, entomology, mycology, anatomy, etc. Many societal issues are biology-based these include biodiversity, genetically modified organisms, reproductive technologies, prolongation of life, food production, tourism industry (biological gardens) and processing industries among the others. The knowledge of biology is not only paramount and useful to the learners only, but to everyone due to its significant to the lives of an individuals and society in general. The mentioned reasons, makes teaching biology necessary and needs to be friendly and relevant in order to make necessary provisions for students' interest and understanding the subject, this can only be achieved by active participation of learners in the teaching and learning process. There are many teacher and student-center teaching strategies that have been developed and used all over the years for teaching the subject, some of which are; lecture method, demonstration method, cooperative learning, problem-solving method, expository method, inquiry-based teaching approach, laboratory activities, peer-tutoring strategy among others. Unfortunately, most teachers teach Biology using predominantly the traditional or lecture method (Aniaku, 2012). Therefore, the proper and effective teaching of Biology cannot be achieved without using student-center teaching strategies in teaching the subject that will help in arousing the student's interest, increase their performance and leads to the high retention ability in the subject. So, to achieve the mentioned issues the present study used laboratory strategy to determine it impact on interest, academic performance and retention in Biology among senior secondary school students of Katsina state, Nigeria. Before then let have insight in the relationship between the dependent and independent variables of the study.

Laboratory has been described as a room or a building specially built for teaching by demonstration of theoretical phenomenon into practical terms. With the laboratory experience, students will be able to translate what they have read in their texts to practical realities, thereby enhancing their understanding of the learnt concepts. Farombi (1998), cited in Yara (2010) argued that seeing is believing is the effect of using laboratories in the teaching and learning of science and other science related disciplines as students tend to understand and recall what they see more than what they hear. Laboratory is very important and essential to the teaching of science and success of any science course is much dependent on the laboratory provision made for it. Lending credence to this statement, Ogunniyi (1982) cited in Yara (2010), said that there is a general consensus among science educators that laboratory occupies a central position in science instruction. It could be conceptualized as a place, where theoretical work is practicalized and practical in any learning experiences involve students in activities such as observing, counting, measuring, experimenting, recording and carrying out fieldwork. According to National Academies Press (NAP; 2023), laboratories as rooms or building in which students use special equipment to carry out research, observation or an investigation about a phenomenon. This may include such activities as chemistry experiments, plant or animal dissections in biology, and investigation of rocks or minerals for identification in earth science. According to Lunetta, 1998; cited in NAP, (2023), defined laboratories as “experiences in school settings in which students interact with materials to observe and understand the natural world”. Practical activities in biology provides opportunities for student to manipulate materials or equipment to investigate and understand the real world around them. Several findings have determined the impact of laboratory activities on student's interest, academic performance and retention in science subjects and Biology in particular some of these findings are mentioned in points below;

Hardr, et.al (2012), in Chibabi, etal. (2018), noted that challenge and satisfaction in laboratory task will motivate students and engage their interest in to the subject taught. According to Nwogbo, (2008) cited in Buba and Marcel, (2019), stated that the practical work in school laboratories gives students appreciation of the spirit of method of problem solving analytical and generalization ability. He maintained that laboratory work fosters students' positive attitudes toward science and maintains their interest in the learning of science subjects. National Academy of Sciences (2010), cited in Buba and Marcel. (2019), recommended that laboratory work was found to be interesting to students and leads to higher academic performance and retrieve past information than non-practical activities in biology. The finding of Ronoh (2013), revealed that the biology laboratory classes might increase the likelihood that students will engage in many experiences that arose their interest, improves performance and higher retention of learned materials.

Laboratory activities plays important role on student's academic performance in science education, Biology included. The findings of Nzewi, 2008 & Aina (2012) in Yusuf and Mukhtar (2019), mentioned that laboratory is an indispensable organ of the school if effective teaching is taking place that will improve students' academic performance. Ronoh, (2013), viewed that laboratory is an instructional facility used by teacher to help students learn about science and how scientists investigate the world around them that will improves their performance. According to Khan and Iqbal (2011), cited in Yusuf and Mukhtar

(2019), students taught using laboratory teaching activities show more performance in science process skills than the students taught using traditional teaching method. The findings of Kitheka, (2005) cited in Kyakuwa, (2017), noted that schools with abundant laboratory resources and proper in utilization of this resource efficiently will boost learning and maximized adequately achieved good academic performance. Also, Adeniyi, (1983) in Kyakuwa (2017), draw attention that there is relationship between teaching with laboratory activities and student's academic performance in teaching science subjects, He maintained that the utilization of laboratory equipment in teaching is significantly related with student's academic performance. This is in-line with Mathew, (1998) cited in Kyakuwa (2017), discovered that utilization of laboratory strategy had positive relationship with student's academic performance towards science teaching and promote good academic performance in the science subjects.

Retention is the ability of the learners to recall information, ideas or learning activities at a later time which he/she may be ask to mention, write or remember after some times. According to Bichi, (2001) cited in Yusuf & Mukhtar (2019) defined retention as the ability to maintain and later recall information or knowledge gained after. Alake (2015), cited in Yusuf and Mukhtar (2019), viewed retention as the ability to store information which can be easily recalled from the short-term memory and long-term memory. The findings of Ajewole & Ivowi in Goje (2014) cited in Yusuf and Mukhtar, (2019), believe that laboratory work helps to promote conceptual understanding which aid in retention of science concepts at a later time. This was supported by findings of Hart, et.al, (2009), cited in Yusuf and Mukhtar (2019), Laboratory activities builds the students' scientific skills and processes especially in learning of science subject in secondary schools thereby enhancing retention ability of science concepts. Based on these premises, we understand the impact of laboratory activities on students' interest, academic performance and retention ability in science subjects, specifically Biology in secondary schools.

To actualize the mastery of the subject matter, learners should be exposed in to different learning strategies that will arouse their interest, increase their academic performance and helps them to have high retention ability. It is on this premise that the researcher examined the impact of laboratory strategy on interest, academic performance and retention in Biology among secondary school students of Katsina state-Nigeria

The persistent students' poor interest, performance and retention of many biology concepts in secondary school level leaves one in doubt about the effectiveness of teaching methods used by Biology teachers for teaching the subjects. Certain factors have been identified by different researchers that attributed to this problem. Buba and Marcel (2019), noted that lack appropriate teaching strategy in teaching is among the factors that influence the problem. Ganyaupfu (2013), mention that factors like lack of science equipment, inadequate qualified Biology teachers, students' overcrowding, poor instructional and infrastructural facilities and use of un-appropriate teaching methods use by Biology teachers are the baseline factors that resulted in poor interest, performance and retention in subject.

Although some researchers and science educators advocate the use of more innovative, result-oriented, and student-centered strategies like laboratory strategy and other student-centered method that involve the total involvement of learners in the teaching and learning process. Opara (2011) noted that these students-centered teaching methods when use in teaching can ultimately and positively affect students' understanding, interest, performance and retention in Biology. Therefore, the problem which this study seeks to solve is laboratory strategy improve students' interest, performance and retention in Biology?

Objectives of the study

1. Determine the mean interest score of students taught biology using laboratory strategy in Katsina State, Nigeria
2. Determine the mean academic performance of students taught biology using laboratory strategy in Katsina state, Nigeria.
3. Determine the mean retention ability of students taught biology using laboratory strategy in Katsina state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean interest of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria?
2. What is the mean academic performance of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria?
3. What is the mean retention ability of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference in mean interest score of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria.

2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in mean academic performance score of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in exposed to Katsina state, Nigeria.
3. **H₀₃**: There is no significant difference in mean retention ability of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state-Nigeria

Methodology

The study employed Pretest, Post-test, Post-post-test and Control group, Quasi-experimental design. The study used two groups; Experimental group (EG) and Control group (CG). The illustration of research design was mentioned below:

Research Design Illustration

Group 1: EG O₁ X₁ O₂ O₃

Group 2: CG O₁ X₀ O₂ O₃

Keys:

EG Experimental Group X₁ Treatment (laboratory strategy)

CG Control Group X₀ No treatment (Lecture method)

O₁ Pre-test

O₂ Post-test

O₃ post-posttest

Population of the Study

The population covered four thousand, five hundred and thirty-one (4,531), Male and Female SS II, Biology Sstudents during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina State-Nigeria.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample size of the study consists of ninety (90), Male, and Female SS II students were selected from the population using Cluster random sampling technique by balloting. The sample was illustrated below

Sample of the study.

S/N	Schools	Status	Male	Female	Total
1	School A	EG	23	18	41
3	School B	CG	26	23	49
	Total		49	41	90

Results

Research Question 1:

Table 2: Mean Ranks of students' Interest Scores toward biology between Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mean Ranks Diff.
Experimental Group	41	63.41	3107.00	39.31
Control Group	49	24.10	988.00	
Total	90			

Table 2. showed that the mean interest of students score in experimental group is (63.41) and that of control group is (24.10). The table indicate that, there is significant difference between the Experimental Group and Control Group with mean rank difference of (39.31). This indicated that, students taught biology using laboratory strategy have high academic performance in biology than those exposed to lecture method.

Research Question 2:

Table 3: Mean difference of students' performance between experimental and control groups.

Groups	N	Mean	Std.	Std. Error Mean	Mean difference
Experimental Group	41	48.37	11.745	1.678	37.96
Control Group	49	10.41	4.416	0.69	

Table 3. showed that the mean academic performance of students score in experimental group is (63.41) and that of control group is (24.10). The table indicate that, there is significant difference between the Experimental Group and Control Group with mean rank difference of (39.31). This indicated that, students taught biology using laboratory strategy have high interest in biology than those exposed to lecture method.

Research Question 3:

Table 4: Mean difference of students' retention between experimental and Control groups

Groups	N	Mean	Std.	Mean difference
Experimental Group	41	37.22	11.852	23.68
Control Group	49	13.54	3.722	

Table 4. showed that the mean retention of students score in experimental group is (63.41) and that of control group is (24.10). The table indicate that, there is significant difference between the Experimental Group and Control Group with mean rank difference of (39.31). This indicated that, students taught biology using laboratory strategy have high retention in biology than those exposed to lecture method.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses formulated were tested using t-test independent between the variables involved. The null hypotheses are rejected when the p-value is less than the alpha-value of 0.05 level of significance and otherwise is retained. The results are presented in tables below and followed by the interpretations as shown below:

H₀₁:

There is no significant difference in mean interest scores of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria.

Table 5: Mann Whitney U-Test for Comparison of Mean Ranks of Interest Score toward Biology for Experimental and Control Groups.

Group	N	Mean	Sum of rank	U-value	p-value	Remark
Experimental Group	49	63.41	3107.00	Z = -	0.0	Significant
Control Group	41	24.10	988.00	7.120		
Total	90					

* Significant at $\alpha \leq 0.05$, U-test = 127.00

Result in Table 5. showed that there exists a statistically significant difference in the mean ranks between the Experimental and Control Groups with Mann-Whitney U test (Z = -7.120) and mean rank difference of 39.48. Since the p-value = 0.0 < 0.05 significant level, the H₀₁ which states that: "There is no significant difference in the interest of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria" is rejected. Hence, there is a significant difference between mean interest scores of the students taught Biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method.

H₀₂:

There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance score of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria.

Table 6: t-test Result on Students Academic Performance in Biology Experimental Group and Control Groups.

Group	N	Mean	Std.	Df	t-value	p-value	Remark
Experimental Group	41	48.37	11.745	88	19.552	0.0	Significant
Control Group	49	10.41	4.416				

* Significant at $\alpha \leq 0.05$

Table 6 showed that p-value (observed) = 0.000 is less than α -value of 0.05 at $df = 88$. Since the observed p-value = 0.000 < 0.05 then the null hypothesis (H02) which states that: “There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance score of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in secondary schools of Katsina state, Nigeria” is rejected. This means that there exists statistically significant difference between Experimental and the Control Groups. Hence, there is significant difference between mean performance scores of the students taught Biology using laboratory strategy and those taught with lecture method.

H03:

There is no significant difference in mean retention ability of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method Katsina state, Nigeria.

Table 7: t-test Result on students' retention score in Biology between Experimental Group one and Control Group.

Group	N	Mean	Std.	Df	t-value	p-value	Remark
Experimental Group	41	37.22	11.852	88	12.29	0.0	Significant
Control Group	49	13.54	3.722				

* Significant at $\alpha \leq 0.05$

Table 7 showed that p-value (observed) = 0.000 is less than α -value of 0.05 at $df = 88$. Since the observed p-value = 0.000 < 0.05 then the null hypothesis (H03) which states that: “There is no significant difference in mean retention ability of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state-Nigeria.” is rejected. This means that there exists statistically significant difference between Experimental Group one and the Control Group. Hence, there is significant difference between the Retention ability of Students taught Biology using laboratory strategy and those taught with lecture method.

The findings revealed that:

1. There is significant difference in mean interest score of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria.
2. There is significant difference in mean academic performance score of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria.
3. There is significant difference in retention ability of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study showed that, there is significant differences in the interest, performance and retention ability of students taught Biology using laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture method. The finding of this study agreed with the findings of Chibabi, et al, (2018), investigated the effect of laboratory method of teaching on senior secondary school students’ achievement and retention in Biology in Kogi East Senatorial Zone. Results of the study revealed that there is significant difference of the achievement, retention and interaction effect between teaching method and the gender of student in the mean gain achievement scores of students taught using laboratory method of teaching and their counterparts taught using lecture method of teaching. In line with findings of Buba and Marcel (2019), carried out study on the effect of practical teaching method on academic achievement of senior secondary biology students in Mubi Educational Zone, Adamawa State. The findings revealed that there is significant difference in the effect of practical method and lecture method on students’ academic achievement in biology. The result also indicated that male students had higher mean score gain than their female counterpart when taught biology using practical method.

Conclusion

Basically, there was a significant difference in mean interest, academic performance and retention scores of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method. Based on the findings it was concluded that laboratory strategy served as better strategy in improving interest, performance and retention in Biology among secondary school students in katsina state.

Recommendations

1. Biology teachers should employ the laboratory strategy in teaching Biology at senior secondary school level. Workshops, conferences and seminars should be organized to Biology teachers by the
2. Ministry of Education on the use of laboratory strategy in teaching Biology at senior secondary school level.
3. Curriculum planners and curriculum development bodies in Nigeria like NERDC should design programme and policies that will incorporate the use of laboratory strategy in teaching and learning biology at Senior Secondary School level.

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